

CONNECT- NM
Coordination of the European
Research Community on Nuclear
Materials for Energy Innovation

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Reporting period	

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Exploitation

Deliverable 3.11 –Open Scientific Guidelines

**Annex B - List of Transformative Agreements (TAs)
within the Consortium**

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PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for partners of CONNECT-NM and the EC	

Annex B - List of Transformative Agreements (TAs) within the Consortium

Institute	Requirements	Journal/ Publishing house	Information
CEA and members of French Couperin Consortium	CC BY 4.0	ACM Association for Computing Machinery	"Publish and Read" agreement 2024-2026 Free gold OA publications of proceedings
		Cambridge University Press	"Publish and Read" agreement 2024-2025 Free gold OA publications in all journals
		EDP Sciences	"Publish and Read" agreement 2022-2026
		Elsevier	"Publish and Read" agreement 2024-2027 Free gold OA publications in all journals except Lancet and Cell Press
		IOP Institute of Physics	"Publish and Read" agreement 2025-2027 Free gold OA publications in 55 hybrid and 21 full OA journals
		PLOS (Public Library of Science)	"Publish and Read" agreement 2025-2026 Free gold OA publications in 14 journals
		Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC)	"Publish and Read" agreement 2025-2027 Limited quantity of vouchers in hybrid journals. 15% discount on APC for gold journals
		Springer Nature	"Publish and Read" agreement 2024-2027 Free gold OA publications in hybrid journals
		Wiley	"Publish and Read" agreement 2022-2025 3164 free articles in gold access in 2025
CIEMAT	CC-BY Licence	Elsevier	A limited number of papers: 2025: 77 2026: 80 2027: 83 2028: 88
		Springer	A limited number of papers: 2025: 13 APC 2026: 13 APC 2027: 13 APC
CNRS	CC BY 4.0 used by default Use of an email address with cnrs.fr domain	American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS)	2024-2026 agreement 7.5% discount on APC for Science Advances
		American Chemical Society (ACS)	"Zero-Embargo Green Open Access agreement" 2024-2026. Author accepted manuscript can be uploaded on an open archive with no embargo
		Association for Computing Machinery (ACM)	"Publish and Read" agreement 2024-2026 Free gold OA publications of proceedings

Institute	Requirements	Journal/ Publishing house	Information
		EDP Sciences	"Publish and Read" agreement 2022-2026. APC waiver in 30 journals for CNRS corresponding authors. Subscribe to open model (no fee for any author) in the rest of journals.
		Elsevier	"Publish and Read" agreement 2024-2027 Free gold OA publications in all journals except Lancet and Cell Press
HZDR	CC-BY Licence	American Chemical Society (ACS)	For all papers in hybrid and gold OA journals
		American Institute of Physics (AIP)	For all papers in hybrid OA journals (not for gold OA journals)
		American Physical Society	For all papers in hybrid OA journals (not for gold OA journals)
		Cambridge University Press (CUP)	For all papers in hybrid and gold OA journals (Standard full collection)
		Elsevier	For all papers in hybrid OA journals (not for gold OA journals)
		Institute of Physics incl. ECS (IOP)	For all papers in hybrid and gold OA journals
		Nature	For all papers in hybrid OA journals (not for gold OA journals)
		Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC)	For all papers in hybrid and gold OA journals
		Sage	For all papers in hybrid OA journals (not for gold OA journals)
		SpringerNature	For all papers in hybrid OA journals (not for gold OA journals)
		Wiley	For all papers in hybrid OA journals (not for gold OA journals)
JSI	The article is ACCEPTED for publication in the year 2025, The corresponding author, or the author submitting the article to the publisher's system, is affiliated with one of the consortium member institutions, Correct specification of the author's institutional affiliation, Author identification	De Gruyter	A limited number of papers in 2025: 3 papers* in hybrid journals (APCs up to 2.300 EUR) * JSI shares the number of papers with other members of Slovenian consortium
		Emerald Publishing	A limited number of papers in 2025: 13 papers* * JSI shares the number of papers with other members of Slovenian consortium
		American Physical Society	Unlimited number of papers in 2025
		American Chemical Society	A limited number of papers in 2025: 81 papers* in hybrid journals and gold OA journals * JSI shares the number of papers with other members of Slovenian consortium

Institute	Requirements	Journal/ Publishing house	Information
	via email address with the institution's domain		
JSI	The article is ACCEPTED for publication in the year 2025, The corresponding author, or the author submitting the article to the publisher's system, is affiliated with one of the consortium member institutions, Correct specification of the author's institutional affiliation, Author identification via email address with the institution's domain	IEEE Xplore	A limited number of papers in 2025: 3 papers in hybrid journals and gold OA journals
		Elsevier	Unlimited number of papers in hybrid journals (but not in gold OA) in 2025
		Taylor & Francis	A limited number of papers in 2025: 85 papers* in "Open Select Standard" hybrid journals 5% discount on APCs in other "Open Select" hybrid journals * JSI shares the number of papers with other members of Slovenian consortium
		Royal Society of Chemistry Gold	Unlimited number of papers in hybrid journals in 2025 15% discount on APCs in gold OA journals (100% discount for some specific gold OA journals)
		Springer Link	A limited number of papers in 2025: 16 papers in hybrid journals
		Wiley Online Library	A limited number of papers in 2025: 139 papers* in hybrid journals 10% discount on APCs in hybrid journals after reaching the paper limit * JSI shares the number of papers with other members of Slovenian consortium
KTH, Chalmers, SSM	The corresponding author must be affiliated with a participating institution	AIP Publishing; American Chemical Society (ACS)	Via the Bibsam agreements (https://www.kb.se/samverkan-och-utveckling/oppen-tillgang-och-bibsamkonsortiet/open-access-and-bibsam-consortium.html), the publishing costs are centrally covered by the institutions that participate in the agreements. Not all institutions participate in all agreements and some institutions have signed additional open access publishing agreements. The range of journals without, or discounted, article processing charges (APCs) for authors may therefore vary between different institutions.
		AIP Publishing; American Chemical Society (ACS)	
		American Physical Society (APS)	
		Association for Computing Machinery (ACM)	
		BMJ Publishing; Brill	

Institute	Requirements	Journal/ Publishing house	Information
KTH, Chalmers, SSM	The corresponding author must be affiliated with a participating institution	Bristol University Press	<p>Via the Bibsam agreements (https://www.kb.se/samverkan-och-utveckling/oppen-tillgang-och-bibsamkonsortiet/open-access-and-bibsam-consortium.html), the publishing costs are centrally covered by the institutions that participate in the agreements.</p> <p>Not all institutions participate in all agreements and some institutions have signed additional open access publishing agreements.</p> <p>The range of journals without, or discounted, article processing charges (APCs) for authors may therefore vary between different institutions.</p>
		Cambridge University Press	
		The Copernicus Publications	
		De Gruyter; eLife	
		Elsevier	
		Emerald	
		Frontiers	
		IOP Publishing	
		IOS Press	
		IWA Publishing	
		JMIR Publications	
		John Benjamins Publishing	
		Karger	
		MDPI	
		MJS Publishing	
		Nature Research Journals	
		Oxford University Press (OUP)	
		PLOS	
		Portland Press	
		Royal Society	
		The Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC)	
		SAGE	
SPIE			
Springer Nature			
Springer Nature Hybrid Journals			
Taylor & Francis			
Wiley			

Institute	Requirements	Journal/ Publishing house	Information
NCBJ	Request for APC waiver Approval of Request by Institution	Elsevier	The program will be launched on May 6th, 2025
		IOP Publishing	Unlimited number of papers in 2025
		Oxford University Press	Estimated launch of the program: May 10th, 2025; Unlimited number of papers in 2025
		Springer	Total number of papers available in the program for 2025: 1378
PoliMI	Request for APC waiver Affiliation of the corresponding author Approval of Request by Institution	ACM Association for Computing Machinery	Read & Publish TA 2022-2025. An unlimited number of papers in hybrid and Gold OA journals. Green OA: authors can deposit the AAM-Author's Accepted Manuscript version of articles freely accessible without embargo
		ACS American Chemical Society	Read & Publish TA 2020-2024 (new agreement has been reached, pending activation. the ability to publish in OA with contract coverage has resumed). A limited number of papers in hybrid journals until the tokens distributed indivisibly on a national basis run out.
		AIP American Institute of Physics	Read & Publish TA 2023-2026. A limited number of papers in hybrid journals for each year: 311 in 2025 323 in 2026
		Elsevier	Read & Publish TA 2023-2027. An unlimited number of papers in hybrid journals from 2025 to the end of Agreement
		Emerald	Read & Publish TA 2025. An unlimited number of papers in hybrid and Gold OA journals Green OA: authors can deposit the AAM-Author's Accepted Manuscript version of articles freely accessible without embargo
		IEEE	Read & Publish TA 2022-2024. The new contract is under negotiation and, starting from January 1, 2025, the OA publication service is suspended until further notice.
		IOP Institute of Physics Publishing	Read & Publish TA 2023-2025. An unlimited number of papers in hybrid and Gold OA journals (the journals of the American Astronomical Society do not participate in the contract)

Institute	Requirements	Journal/ Publishing house	Information
PoliMI	Request for APC waiver Affiliation of the corresponding author Approval of Request by Institution	OUP Oxford University Press	Read & Publish TA 2024-2026. An unlimited number of papers in hybrid journals Green OA: authors can deposit the AAM-Author's Accepted Manuscript version of articles freely accessible without embargo
		RSC	Read & Publish TA 2025. A limited number of papers, until the tokens distributed indivisibly on a national basis run out, in hybrid journals and in hybrid OA journals which become Gold OA journals during the term of the contract.
		Springer	Read & Publish TA 2020- June 2025. (extension, new contract in the process of renewal). A limited number of papers in hybrid journals until the tokens distributed indivisibly on a national basis run out.
		Wiley	Read & Publish TA 2024-2027. A limited number of papers in hybrid and Gold OA journals until the tokens distributed indivisibly on a national basis run out.
STUBA	Request for APC waiver Approval of Request by Institution and Journal	Elsevier	A limited number of papers: 5 papers in hybrid journals per year 19 papers in gold OA journals
		IEEE	A limited number of papers: 13 papers per year
		Springer Nature	A limited number of papers: 293 tokens per year
UPM	Request for APC waiver Approval of Request by Institution and Journal	Cambridge University Press	Unlimited number of papers in 2025
		Elsevier	Unlimited number of papers in 2025
		IEEE	A limited number of papers: 44 papers in 2025
		Springer	A limited number of papers: 57 papers in 2025
		Wiley	A limited number of papers: 28 papers in 2025
VTT	CC BY 4.0	Elsevier	Agreement – 31.12.2025 Without article processing charge (APC) in Elsevier hybrid journals and journals flipped from hybrid to gold open access (xlsx) With 15 % discount of the journal's APC in Elsevier gold open access journals (xlsx) .

Institute	Requirements	Journal/ Publishing house	Information
		IEEE	Agreement – 31.12.2025 Limited amount of free open access articles
		Institute of Physics - IOP	Agreement 2025-2027 Applies to all primary research article types
		Wiley	Agreement 2025-2026
ZAG	the article is accepted for publication in 2025, the corresponding author, or the author submitting the paper to the publisher's system, is from one of the consortium members, the correct details (name) of the author's institution, Identification of the author by e-mail address with the institution's domain.	Elsevier	An unlimited number of papers in journals listed here: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/166MivJbeDb7CXpV7QDWBrmqp-mI5XcnDFKZJDZJGsuE/edit?gid=1766009349#gid=1766009349
		Springer Nature	A limited number of papers: 3 papers in 2025 in journals listed here: https://resource-cms.springernature.com/springer-cms/rest/v1/content/26206374/data/v11

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